

Results of the AfriAlliance survey on drivers for Participating in Working Groups

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The AfriAlliance project is trying to foster the successful interaction among relevant stakeholders from both Africa and Europe, in water management. This is of principal importance when trying to generate, increase and exchange knowledge and innovation for solutions that have noticeable and high impact.

Working Groups, Action Groups, or Communities of Practice – these are all means to bring together relevant stakeholders, experts and/or decision makers to engage in joint knowledge creation and knowledge sharing around a specific topic, issue or area. But these are only useful means if people actually want to participate in such groups.

Since AfriAlliance is trying enhance African preparedness for Climate Change challenges, we have asked you - African and other stakeholders with an interest in the African context - to share your views and experiences of participating in Working Groups. We asked: What are the barriers and obstacles for your participation in Working Groups? What is in it for you? And under what conditions do you think they work well?

These views were collected via an online survey that was available from 27 June until 3 July 2016 and which generated almost 100 responses (98 in total), with 44 from Africa, 33 from Europe, 3 respondents from elsewhere (plus 18 non-disclosed). The responses came from diverse stakeholder organisations, with the vast majority having previous experience with Working Groups and most of them male (60 vs 20 female & 18 non-disclosed).

The survey results in a nutshell

Here we present a summary of the results, which are clustered into three main categories:

1. Perceived positive and negative outcomes of participation
2. Social pressures to participate
3. Opportunities and barriers for participation

1. Perceived outcomes of participating in Working Groups in an African context

Positive outcomes of participation	Negative outcomes of participation
A. Organizational outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expenses (travel, accommodation) - Time - Impact for strategic position (ideas stolen, no IP protection) - Undesirable outcomes (poor/'not practical' outcomes, waste of resources, discontinued collaboration after a while)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Exchange knowledge/experience/ideas/opinions ✓ Networking and finding new opportunities (e.g. identify new partners and collaboration possibilities) ✓ Enhance strategic position of our organisation (exposure and leveraging new/relevant ideas) ✓ Alignment with organisation's interest and activities ✓ Marketing (promotion of products/services) ✓ Capacity building ✓ Enhancement of resources (reduce costs, save time, technology exchange) ✓ Opportunity to influence donors and policy makers, future collaboration 	
B. Personal outcomes	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Exchange knowledge/experience/ideas/opinions ✓ Networking and finding new opportunities ✓ Alignment with my personal (research) interest and activities 	
C. Societal outcomes	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contribution to development ✓ Bring interest/opportunities to the region/to Africa ✓ Policy relevance (what does/doesn't work and how policies can be improved) 	

2. **Social pressure** to participate in Working Groups in an African context – where does it stem from?

Pressure to participate stems from...	Pressure NOT to participate stems from...
A. Organisational pressure	A. Organisational pressure
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Superiors/management ✓ Colleagues/peers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Superiors/management - Colleagues/peers
B. Institutional pressure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Governmental organizations (Ministries, policy makers, agencies) ✓ Researchers/research institutes ✓ Regional organizations ✓ Civil society/ local community ✓ NGOs ✓ Local authorities ✓ Private sector ✓ International organizations ✓ Donors ✓ Local leaders 	
C. Moral norms and values	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Personal values/altruism/cultural traditions ✓ International cooperation ✓ Local development 	

3. Opportunities and barriers for participating in Working Groups in an African context

Enabling factors/circumstances for participation	Barriers & obstacles for participation
A. Strategic position	A. Strategic position
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Synergies with existing projects/mission ✓ Alignment with personal interests, experience and skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conflict of interests - Other priorities/workload
B. Resources	B. Resources
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Control over resources (cost, time, ideas, means of communication, internet connection) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of control over resources (time, cost, human resources, means of communication) - Lack of technical and interpersonal skills - Lack of language skills (e.g. English)
C. Structure and functioning	C. Structure and functioning
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Good cooperation, management and functioning (communication, consultation, Flexible participation methods (e.g. online participation) , partnership, co-decision making, and co-production, clear objectives, defined responsibilities, clear envisioned outcomes, establishment of a charter or ToR) ✓ Inclusiveness (e.g. inclusion of diverse stakeholders and local communities) ✓ Facilitation, support of the working group (e.g. reimbursement of resources spent (time, costs), coaching young participants) ✓ Evidence of usefulness of the WG activities in terms of societal outcomes, e.g. link to the SDGs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ineffective/inappropriate/inefficient composition and functioning of the WG (e.g. passive members, duplication of efforts, lengthy discussions, ideas taken lightly, complex organization, poor agenda management, uneven support of members, no feedback system, no documentation of activities) - Lack of inclusiveness re. local/African stakeholders
D. Feedback and acknowledgement	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Support and acknowledgement from local/regional decision making bodies (e.g. Ministries) ✓ Tangible results and recognition of the efforts by the WG (e.g. in publications) 	

What do these results mean for AfriAlliance?

We are now aligning the AfriAlliance project activities with your expectations to the best of our abilities.

Right now, we have a **Call for Applications** to create demand-driven, problem-focused AfriAlliance Action Groups. These Action Groups will bring together African and European peers with **relevant knowledge, expertise and solutions**.

Based on the survey results, AfriAlliance provides the Action Groups with **focus and structure, support, seed funding and outreach opportunities** so that the groups can work effectively and can identify and address vulnerabilities.

The activities of an Action Group will focus on one issue under the following themes:

- Integrated Water Resource Management
- Food Security / Agriculture
- Human Capacity Development
- Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation
- Water and Climate Data monitoring collection forecasting and analysis

If you want to apply to create an AfriAlliance Action Group, please click here:

<http://afrialliance.org/action-groups-call-for-applications/>

You can apply any time **before 31 July 2016**.

The full analysis and discussion of the survey results will be available in a forthcoming academic publication. If you would like to be informed about this or know more about AfriAlliance, please get in touch with us:

afrialliance@unesco-ihe.org (email)

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